

Synthesis of ruthenium(II) complex with a hexadentate N₂O₂S₂ donor azo-thioether ligand : X-Ray structure, electrochemistry and DFT calculation

Subrata Jana, Ajoy Kumar Pramanik, Chandan Kumar Manna and Tapan Kumar Mondal*

Inorganic Chemistry Section, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University,
Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : tapank.mondal@jadavpuruniversity.in

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Abstract : A ruthenium(II) complex (Ru-L) with hexadentate thioether containing N₂O₂S₂ donor azo functional ligand (H₂L) is synthesized and characterized by several spectroscopic techniques. Structure of the complex is confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. The complex exhibits two successive Ru^{II}/Ru^{III} and Ru^{III}/Ru^{IV} oxidation couples along with a ligand based reduction in cyclic voltammetric study. The electronic structure and redox property of the complex are interpreted by DFT calculation. The electronic transitions, calculated by TDDFT/CPCM method are used to assign the UV-Vis absorption bands.

Keywords : Ruthenium(II) complex, N₂O₂S₂ donor thioether ligand, X-ray and electronic structure, electrochemistry, DFT and TDDFT calculations.

Introduction

There is considerable interest in the coordination chemistry of polydentate macrocyclic ligands and in the recent years enormous progress has been made in macrocyclic chemistry¹. The macrocyclic ligands having N, S and O donor atoms are designed with enhanced ability to encapsulate given metal ions selectively² which can influence the course of many complicated reactions occurring during metabolic activity in living organisms³. The coordination chemistry of transition metals with multidentate ligands having N and S donor atoms have gained augmented research interest in recent years owing to their diverse potential applications in biomedicine, biological imaging, catalysis and solar cell⁴. The study of compounds containing N and S atoms has also greater attention due to their significant antifungal, antibacterial and anticancer activities⁵.

The coordination chemistry of transition metals with thioether ligands is a field of interest for their

stability, chemical, electrochemical and biological activities⁶. Thioether containing azo ligands can stabilize metal ions in unusual oxidation states and with uncommon coordination numbers⁷. Since nitrogen atom is at borderline while sulphur atom belongs to soft base in the theory of soft-hard acid and base, multidentate ligands containing these two donor atoms bind to a wide range of transition metals⁸. Thioether containing azo ligands with acetylacetonate and their transition metal complexes are reported⁹. In continuation to synthesis of thioaryazo ligands and their transition metal complexes¹⁰, herein we have synthesized ruthenium(II) complex (Ru-L) with the reported hexadentate N₂O₂S₂ donor azo functional ligand (H₂L)¹¹. The octahedral geometry of the ruthenium(II) complex is confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. Electrochemical property of the complex is investigated by cyclic voltammetric study. Electronic structure and solution spectra of the complex are interpreted by DFT and TDDFT calculations.

*Invited Lecture.

Experimental

Materials

All the reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and used as received. Acetyl acetone and inorganic metal salts were available from E. Merck, India. $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminothiophenol and 1,2-dibromoethane were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. 1,2-Bis(2-amino-phenylthio)ethane and ligand H_2L were prepared following the published procedure^{11,12}.

Physical measurements

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer CHN-2400 elemental analyzer. Electronic spectra were measured on Lambda 750 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in acetonitrile solution. IR spectra were recorded on RX-1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the spectral range 4000–400 cm^{-1} with the samples in the form of KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometers in presence of TMS as internal standard. Cyclic voltammetric measurements were carried out using a CHI Electrochemical workstation. A platinum wire working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used in a standard three-electrode configuration. $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ was used as the supporting electrolyte and the scan rate used was 50 mV s^{-1} in acetonitrile under argon atmosphere.

Synthesis of ruthenium(II) complex (Ru-L)

$\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (55 mg, 0.201 mmol), was dissolved in 15 mL of hot acetonitrile with constant stirring. The mixture was then heated to reflux for 2 h. The deep brown solution changed to dark green. To it 15 mL acetonitrile solution of H_2L (100 mg, 0.201 mmol) was added drop wise and finally refluxed for 12 h to yield a deep red solution. The reaction mixture was cooled and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The red crude solid product was then dissolved in minimum volume of CH_2Cl_2 and purified by using a silica gel column. With CH_2Cl_2 - CH_3CN (3 : 1), a deep red compound corresponding to the com-

plex was eluted. The desired red product corresponds to ruthenium(II) complex, Ru-L was collected upon evaporation of the solvent. Yield was 73 mg (61%).

Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2\text{Ru}$ (Ru-L) : C, 48.23; H, 4.05; N, 9.37. Found (%) : C, 48.1; H, 4.0; N, 9.3%; IR data (KBr disc) (cm^{-1}) : 2937 $\nu(\text{C-H})$, 1673 $\nu(\text{C=O})$, 1586 $\nu(\text{C=N})$, 1405 $\nu(\text{N=N})$; ^1H NMR data in CDCl_3 (δ , ppm) : 7.91 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.42–7.56 (4H, m), 7.16 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 3.12 (4H, s), 2.63 (6H, s), 2.55 (6H, s); ESI-mass in acetonitrile : m/z , $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+ = 620.2$; λ_{max} (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) in acetonitrile : 505 (4887), 450 (sh.), 360 (10646), 307 (18426); $E_{1/2}(\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}})$: 0.72 V ($\Delta E = 75$ mV), 1.44 ($\Delta E = 146$ mV); $E_{1/2}(\text{L}/\text{L}^{\bullet-})$: -1.12 V ($\Delta E = 110$ mV).

Computational details

Full geometry optimization of Ru-L complex was carried out using the density functional theory method at the B3LYP level¹³. All elements except ruthenium were assigned the 6-31G(d) basis set. The LanL2DZ basis set with effective core potential was employed for the ruthenium atom¹⁴. The vibrational frequency calculation was performed to ensure that the optimized geometry represents the local minima and there are only positive eigenvalues. All calculations were performed with Gaussian09 program package¹⁵. Vertical electronic excitations based on the optimized geometry were computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) formalism¹⁶ in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)¹⁷. GaussSum¹⁸ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

Crystal structure determination and refinement

The crystals of Ru-L were grown by slow diffusion of dichloromethane solution of the complex into n-hexane. Single crystal data collections were performed with an automated Bruker AXS Kappa smart Apex-II diffractometer equipped with an Apex-II CCD area detector using a fine focus sealed tube as the radiation source of graphite mono-

chromator Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Details of crystal analyses, data collection and structure refinement data are given in Table 1. Reflection data were recorded using the ω scan technique. Unit cell parameters were determined from

Formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Ru
Formula weight	597.68
Crystal color	Red
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C ₂ /c
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	23.984(5), 11.123(5), 21.013(5)
β (°)	115.615(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	5055(3)
<i>Z</i>	8
D (Calcd.) (g/cm ³)	1.571
Mu (MoK α) (mm)	0.824
F(000)	2432
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Radiation (Å)	0.71073
θ (Min-Max) (°)	2.15–26.41
Data set (<i>h</i> ; <i>k</i> ; <i>l</i>)	–30 to 30; –12 to 13; –23 to 26
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.21 × 0.15 × 0.13
Total, Unique Data, R(int)	19218, 5130, 0.0545
Observed data (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	3328
Nref, Npar	5130, 316
R ₁ ^a , wR ₂ ^b	0.0799, 0.2050
Residual Density (e/Å ³)	–1.171 and 1.019
Goodness of fit (GOF) ^c	1.069
^a R ₁ = $\Sigma(F_o - F_c) / \Sigma F_o $	
^b wR ₂ = $\{\Sigma[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \Sigma[w(F_o^2)^2]\}^{1/2}$,	
$w = 1 / [\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0952P)^2 + 50.1234P]$, where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2) / 3$	
^c GOF = $\{\Sigma[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (n-p)\}^{1/2}$, where <i>n</i> = number of measured data and <i>p</i> = number of parameters.	

least-squares refinement of setting angles θ within a definite range respectively. The absorption corrections were done by the multi-scan technique. The data were reduced and integrated using the SAINT¹⁹ program. A semi-empirical multi-scan absorption correction was made with SADABS²⁰. The structures were solved by direct methods employing WinGX²¹ and SHELXS-97²² programs. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically by full-matrix least-squares method with SHELXL-97²². Hydrogen atoms were generated in the refinement process as per the riding model with thermal parameters equal to 1.2 times that of associated C atoms, and participated in the calculation of the final R-indices. Figures of the structure was drawn with ORTEP-32²³ program with 35% ellipsoidal probability.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and spectral characterization

New ruthenium(II) complex with thioether containing hexadentate N₂O₂S₂ donor azo functional ligand (H₂L) is synthesized by the reaction of RuCl₃·3H₂O and H₂L in 1 : 1 ratio under refluxing condition in acetonitrile (Scheme 1). The complex is thoroughly characterized by several spectroscopic techniques. The ¹H NMR signals in CDCl₃ well support the proposed structure of the complex. Two sharp singlets for -CH₃ protons appeared at 2.63 and 2.55 ppm. The methylene protons of S-alkyl part appeared at 3.12 ppm as sharp singlet. The aromatic protons appeared at 7.16–7.91 ppm. IR spectrum of the complex exhibits characteristic ν (C=O), ν (C=N) and ν (N=N)

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Ru-L complex using H₂L ligand.

stretching at 1673, 1586, and 1405 cm^{-1} respectively. The (N=N) stretching in the complex significantly reduced compare to free ligand value (1432 cm^{-1})¹² suggesting the coordination of azo-N to ruthenium. The UV-Vis spectrum in acetonitrile exhibits moderate intense low energy band at 505 nm (ϵ , $4887 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) along with a shoulder at 450 nm. In addition two sharp peaks at 360 nm (ϵ , $10646 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 307 nm (ϵ , $18426 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were observed (Fig. 1). ESI mass spectrum of the complex exhibits a peak with m/z at 600 corresponds to $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ species.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of Ru-L in acetonitrile.

X-Ray structure of Ru-L

The ORTEP plot with atom numbering scheme of ruthenium(II) complex (Ru-L) is shown in Fig. 2. The coordination sphere around ruthenium is distorted octahedral as revealed from the metric parameters (Table 2). The ligand H_2L binds to the metal using its entire six coordination site (O, azo-N and thioether-S). In the octahedral geometry the two thioether-S donors and two O-donors are *cis* to each other, while azo-N donor pair displaced *trans* to each other in the complex. The N2-Ru1-S1 and N3-Ru1-S2 chelate bite angles $85.72(14)^\circ$ and $84.71(14)^\circ$ are significantly deviates from 90° and that's led to the distortion in the octahedral geometry. Other chelate bite angles are

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot with 35% ellipsoidal probability of Ru-L.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (\AA) and bond angles ($^\circ$) of Ru-L

Bonds (\AA)	X-Ray	Calcd.
Ru1-N2	2.101(5)	2.115
Ru1-N3	2.101(5)	2.116
Ru1-O1	2.047(4)	2.071
Ru1-O3	2.033(4)	2.071
Ru1-S1	2.4099(18)	2.425
Ru1-S2	2.4128(18)	2.425
N1-N2	1.305(6)	1.285
N3-N4	1.294(6)	1.285
Angles ($^\circ$)		
N2-Ru1-N3	176.01(19)	178.0
N2-Ru1-O1	86.81(18)	88.27
N2-Ru1-O3	87.03(18)	89.27
N2-Ru1-S1	85.72(14)	84.91
N2-Ru1-S2	94.70(15)	95.51
N3-Ru1-O1	97.17(18)	93.25
N3-Ru1-O3	87.03(18)	89.27
N3-Ru1-S1	90.31(14)	93.51
N3-Ru1-S2	84.71(14)	84.91
O1-Ru1-O3	86.23(19)	86.97
O1-Ru1-S1	172.52(13)	174.2
O1-Ru1-S2	94.37(14)	92.12
O3-Ru1-S1	93.91(14)	92.13
O3-Ru1-S2	171.73(13)	174.1
S1-Ru1-S2	86.57(7)	88.34

also slightly deviated from 90° in the complex (Table 2). The Ru1-N2 and Ru1-N3 bond distances ($2.101(5) \text{ \AA}$ and $2.101(5) \text{ \AA}$) are found to be as expected¹⁰. The Ru-S(thioether) bond distances are

well correlated with the reported Ru-S bond distances⁹.

DFT and TDDFT calculations

To get detailed insight into the electronic structure of Ru-L, DFT calculations were performed using DFT/B3LYP method. The optimized bond distances and bond angles are summarized in Table 2. The calculated Ru-O, Ru-N(azo) and Ru-S(thioether) bond distances are well correlated with the X-ray distances.

The energies along with compositions of some selected molecular orbitals are given in Table 3. The HOMO, HOMO-1 and HOMO-3 have significant contribution of $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals (39–55%) along with the contribution of $\pi(\text{L})$ (45–61%) orbitals (Fig. 3). HOMO-2 has $\pi(\text{L})$ character (97%) while HOMO-4 to HOMO-7 have mixed character of $\pi(\text{L})$ and $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals. The LUMO and LUMO+1 have $\pi^*(\text{L})$ character with significant contribution of N=N function. The HOMO-LUMO energy gap in the complex is found to be 3.15 eV.

Table 3. Energy and compositions of selected molecular orbitals of Ru-L

MO	Energy	% Composition	
		Ru	L
LUMO+5	-0.36	01	99
LUMO+4	-0.56	24	76
LUMO+3	-0.93	06	94
LUMO+2	-1.01	03	97
LUMO+1	-1.91	04	96 (N=N, 35)
LUMO	-1.96	03	97 (N=N, 37)
HOMO	-5.11	48	52
HOMO-1	-5.30	39	61
HOMO-2	-6.00	03	97
HOMO-3	-6.02	55	45
HOMO-4	-6.16	25	75
HOMO-5	-6.33	26	74
HOMO-6	-6.33	14	86
HOMO-7	-6.69	15	85 (N=N, 52)
HOMO-8	-7.23	01	99
HOMO-9	-7.34	03	97
HOMO-10	-7.44	16	84

To get detailed insight into the electronic transitions of the complex TDDFT calculation on the optimized geometry of Ru-L was performed. Some

Fig. 3. Contour plots of selected molecular orbitals of Ru-L.

Table 4. Vertical electron excitation calculated by TDDFT/CPCM method of Ru-L

λ (nm)	E (eV)	Osc. strength (f)	Key excitations	Character	$\lambda_{\text{Expt.}}$ (nm) ($\epsilon, \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)
536.9	2.3092	0.0176	(90%)HOMO \rightarrow LUMO	$d\pi(\text{Ru})/\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ MLCT/ILCT	505 (4887)
523.6	2.3681	0.0135	(89%)HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1	$d\pi(\text{Ru})/\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ MLCT/ILCT	
472.9	2.6219	0.0618	(51%)HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (44%)HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO	$d\pi(\text{Ru})/\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ MLCT/ILCT	450 (sh.)
384.8	3.2220	0.0948	(87%)HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO	$\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ ILCT	360 (10646)
331.3	3.7427	0.2528	(74%)HOMO-6 \rightarrow LUMO	$\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ ILCT	307 (18426)
312.5	3.9674	0.1035	(85%)HOMO-6 \rightarrow LUMO+2	$\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ ILCT	

selected calculated vertical electronic transitions are summarized in Table 4. The peak at 505 nm of the complex corresponds to HOMO \rightarrow LUMO ($\lambda = 537$ nm, $f = 0.018$) and HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 ($\lambda = 524$ nm, $f = 0.014$) transitions having mixed metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) and intra-ligand charge transfer (ILCT) in character. The shoulder at 450 nm also has mixed MLCT and ILCT character. The high energy band at 360 nm corresponds to HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO transition ($\lambda = 385$ nm, $f = 0.253$) and has ILCT character (Table 4).

Electrochemistry

The electrochemical behavior of the complex was investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV) in presence of $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ in acetonitrile at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} . The complex exhibits one reversible and one quasi-reversible oxidative peaks at 0.72 V ($\Delta E = 75 \text{ mV}$) and 1.44 V ($\Delta E = 146 \text{ mV}$) respectively. When scanned in the negative potential range a quasi-reversible reduction peak at -1.12 V ($\Delta E = 110 \text{ mV}$) was appeared (Fig. 4). The successive two oxidation peaks are assigned as the oxidation of Ru^{II} to Ru^{III} and Ru^{III} to Ru^{IV} respectively as the HOMO of the complex has 48% $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ character. Similarly, the quasi-

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of Ru-L in acetonitrile.

reversible reduction peak is assigned as the reduction coordinated ligand because LUMO has 97% $\pi(\text{L})$ character.

Conclusion

New ruthenium(II) complex, Ru-L with thioether containing hexadentate $\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ donor azo ligand (H_2L) is synthesized and characterized. The pseudo octahedral geometry of the complex is confirmed by single crystal X-ray structure analysis. The complex exhibits two successive $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/$

Ru^{IV} oxidation couples along with a ligand based reduction in cyclic voltammetric study. The electronic structure of the complex is well interpreted by DFT calculation. The spin allowed electronic transitions computed by TDDFT method successfully interpret the UV-Vis spectrum of the complex in acetonitrile.

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Supplementary materials

Crystallographic data for the structure Ru-L has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 1036745. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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